

The following is the text of an interview that was published in July 2004 on the website of the European Commission's FP6 Marie Curie Actions programme. It used to be accessible via http://europa.eu.int/comm/research/fp6/mariecurie-actions/news/interview15_en.html#4 (this link is no longer functional).

This interview was part of a set of interviews with five young researchers (Eleanna Galanaki / Fabienne Goldfarb / Marius Linguraru / Dagmar Meyer / Augusto Palombini) who were asked about their experience of mobility and all answered the same questions. The interviews were conducted at the occasion of the launch of the European Network of Mobility Centres (ERA-MORE), which took place in Paris on 29-30 June 2004.

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Young researchers in motion

(interview #4: Dagmar Meyer)

Dagmar studied mathematics at the universities of Heidelberg, Germany and Cambridge, UK. Her Ph.D. studies in algebraic topology were split between the Autonomous University of Barcelona and the Max-Planck Institute for Mathematics in Bonn. She spent two years doing postdoctoral research at the University of Paris XIII, funded by an EU Marie Curie fellowship. In 2001, she returned to her native Germany to take up a position as assistant professor at the University of Göttingen. She is currently Chair of the Marie Curie Fellowship Association (<http://www.mariecurie.org>).

1. What are, for you, the main benefits that a young researcher can expect from career mobility – geographical or otherwise?

Usually when you decide to be mobile you have scientific (and possibly economic) reasons to do so – better equipment at the host institution, the opportunity to work with world experts in your field, better working conditions in general (depending where you come from). If it then turns out that these expectations are not fulfilled, it can be quite a let-down! Being mobile inevitably means that you will enlarge your network of scientific and personal contacts, and this is an extremely important factor for your career development. However, there is another benefit that is probably at least as important: moving to another environment (be it another country or moving between sectors) always implies quite a challenge and thereby an opportunity for personal growth. If you master it then you can be sure that you have learned something for life, regardless of what kind of career you decide to follow later on.

2. What still remains to be done on a European level to make the experience of mobility a really positive one for young researchers?

Mobile researchers are still losing way too much time on unnecessary paperwork related to their mobility. Social security systems across Europe need to be harmonised before we can speak of a system that truly encourages people to move in order to fully realise their potential. Much work also remains to be done regarding entry conditions for researchers from non-EU Member States, and their families. In this respect, a number of initiatives have been

launched at European level, but they can only be effective if they are put into action by all the players involved – all the way down to the level of individual institutions.

3. Do you have a favourite personal anecdote from your own experience which illustrates the problems or pleasures of mobility?

I first came to France with a postdoctoral grant from the French Ministry of Foreign Affairs. As soon as I arrived I went to the Préfecture to apply for my residence permit. I showed them the lettre de présentation from the French Embassy in Bonn and was treated very well – the whole procedure took barely ten minutes. I then told the lady who was helping me that my partner would also need a residence permit. We were not married, and when she heard that I was going to support him until he found a job her attitude changed completely. The smile disappeared from her face and she told him in a pretty rough manner: “You have three months. If you don’t have a job by then you go back to where you came from.” At this moment I realised that even in a country like France not all men are equal...

4. Is an experience in a good foreign laboratory an important factor in clinching a permanent position back in Europe or, on the contrary, does being away for a year or two reduce your chances of being employed again in your home country?

Unfortunately, in some countries it is very hard for researchers to reintegrate after a stay abroad, due to a culture of nepotism and highly opaque recruitment procedures. The ‘Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers’ the Commission is currently developing might help to change this, provided that institutions can be convinced about subscribing to it. Changing mentalities is a very slow process that needs more than declarations of political will at European level – in the end, only economic incentives or sanctions will produce the desired changes. What the individual researcher can do to facilitate her or his move back is to keep in contact with the scientific community at home at all times. Host institutions should support the participation of long-term visiting researchers in conferences in the home country and research visits to the home institution, appreciating that they could also greatly benefit from the lasting collaborations that could grow out of this.

5. The time when researchers are most likely to want to experience mobility often coincides with a time when they are also thinking about starting a family. How does mobility affect personal relationships and family life?

Mobility can imply a real challenge for your partnership. Quite often the scientific and professional advancement of one partner means a period of unemployment for the other, or a job that doesn’t correspond to her or his qualifications, with detrimental effects on their careers. In some places special offices now exist that help foreign researchers to find adequate employment for their partners, but such services are the exception rather than the rule. Mobile researchers with children have to face even more problems: if the family stays behind, the long separation can be very hard psychologically for both parents and children; if the family comes along they have to worry about childcare and schooling in a foreign country, which can be quite difficult if they don’t receive any local support. Host institutions often overlook this dimension of mobility, seeing only the researcher they employ without worrying about her or his personal circumstances.

6. In many European countries there seems to be a penury of permanent positions for young researchers, making it very difficult for expatriate researchers to come back to their country of origin or another European country. What initiatives need to be put in place to help expatriate researchers come back to Europe?

Re-attracting expatriate researchers who have left Europe is one thing – making Europe an attractive place to work so that (young) researchers don’t permanently emigrate is another. Recruitment procedures should take into account the mobility of an applicant in an appropriate way: while the simple fact that somebody has spent time abroad should not be

treated as a plus in itself, the qualifications acquired through such an experience (which are often subtle and intangible) should be given the value that they deserve. On the other hand, the best way to avoid a permanent 'brain drain' is to create real opportunities and long-term career perspectives for young researchers within Europe. More permanent or long-term positions are needed, and an appropriate balance between security and flexibility must be found. Research careers need to become more compatible with the personal life-planning of the individuals concerned, allowing for a healthy family and social life. Oversimplifying this slightly, you could say: "Only a happy researcher is a good researcher".

7. Is there enough incentive for researchers to try out other forms of mobility, such as moving from the public to the private sector, from basic and applied research, or from research and teaching, for example?

As with geographical mobility, mobility between sectors or disciplines should not be a goal in itself but should always be motivated by a real desire to move in order to acquire new competencies, learn new techniques and find new ways of applying knowledge. The real problem lies in the lack of information about the variety of opportunities that exist 'off the beaten track', and a certain lack of willingness to take on risk. Moving to a new research environment is always connected to risk, and people would like to keep an escape route open so they can move back if the experiment fails. However, the structures that are currently in place make it very difficult to move back to academia once you have moved out of it for a certain time. Improving the dialogue between academia and the commercial sector in general would also facilitate the mobility of researchers between them.